

REALIZATION OF LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL UNITS IN THE LINGUISTIC LANDSCAPE OF THE WORLD

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Annotation This article gives features how the significance of the linguoculturalology has grown over the years with supporting ideas for how language plays an important role in the life of human beings. The main mention in it is that language is not only functioned as tool of communication but also used to build the life of its speaker in all aspects

Key words: Linguoculturalology, anthrological paradigm, speech culture, equivalence,lexeme.

As a separate field of science and science, linguoculturalology, which arose at the intersection of language and culture, is required to have its own research object, subject, goals and tasks. In this case, first of all, it is necessary to clarify the general descriptive features of linguistic and cultural studies. V. N. Telia quotes the tariff that "Linguoculturalology is a science that studies the human, or more precisely, the cultural factor in a person." This means that at the center of linguo-cultural science is a complex of achievements typical of the anthropological paradigm of the human phenomenon. According to G.G. Slisshkin, "Linguoculturalology is focused on the human factor, more precisely, on the cultural factor in a person. The fact that the center of linguoculturalology consists of the phenomenon of culture indicates that the science of man is a phenomenon belonging to the anthropological paradigm. The issue of the relationship between language and culture has complex and contradictory aspects. No matter how this problem is interpreted by scientists, it is important for linguistics, especially linguo-culturology, to determine the role of the human factor in the language and the perception of the cultural value system by

language speakers. Prof. As N. Mahmudov said, "language and culture usually mean explaining this or that culture through language or, conversely, by studying culture. To be more precise, the meaning of culture in linguo-culturology is "the level achieved in mental-spiritual or economic activity, not "level (speech culture)", but "a set of achievements of human society in production, social and spiritual-educational life (cultural history, Uzbek culture)".

Two cultures are never completely compatible. These inconsistencies are also observed in the lexical-semantic, functional, stylistic and grammatical features of the linguo-cultural units of the compared languages. The fact that some units belonging to this layer have equivalents in the second language being compared does not indicate that these units are linguistically equivalent. Because the conceptsphere existing in the cognitive linguistic world of a representative of one culture may be perceived as a reality or lacuna phenomenon in the language of a representative of another culture or may exist in a non-verbalized state. These features of linguistic and cultural units become clearer when they are analyzed on a comparative basis, described and classified taking into account the semantic-structural characteristics of both languages.

Equivalent linguocultural units not only record intercultural compatibility, but also reveal their distinguishing features. In the comparison of languages, lexical units that are similar in form, but whose content components are not similar to each other, are congruent phenomena; Although not similar in form, lexical units whose content components are consistent with each other create the phenomenon of equivalence. The phenomenon of equivalence describes the relationship of two corresponding units, but these units do not form all connections. Each thing in the universe characterizes its own sign, and this thing is not uniformly perceived by representatives of one or another culture. For this reason, representatives of different nationalities can trace different "traces" behind the same concept.

An equivalent unit is a national-cultural word or phrase that does not exist in the structural components of the corresponding equivalent in the language under

comparison, and it is a lexical unit that does not form exactly with the same national-cultural component.

In English, the lack of a combination of money, sarpo, material, etc. given by the groom to the girl in accordance with the agreement between the bridegroom and the equivalent of the wedding in Uzbek is explained by the absence of such a situation in English culture. Functionality is also observed in linguistic and cultural units. In this case, the resulting unit can be used in one or more meanings that are not related to culture, while reflecting traits related to a particular culture. The description of the wedding lexeme given in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language also proves our opinion. But there are no cases where the lexeme wedding in English is used in the semantic sense given above.

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